

The Effect of Metal Ion in *Bis*(*N-n*-butyl, salim) Metal(II) on the Dehalogenation of Chloroform

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The effect of metal ion on the dehalogenation of chloroform promoted by the ligand substitution reaction system, consisting of *bis*(*N-n*-butyl, salim) metal(II) [with metal(II)=Zn(II), Cu(II), Ni(II), Pt(II) and Pd(II)] and *N, N, N', N'*-tetramethylethylenediamine has been studied. The above study of kinetics was followed by the measurement of rate of chloride release at four different temperatures. Electronegativity of the metal ion and the stereochemistry of the complex were found to control the rate of reaction. A relationship between the electronegativity of metal ion and the energy of activation has been observed. Furthermore, a relationship between the energy of activation and the downfield chemical shift of the methine proton has been obtained. These observations substantiate the nature of the proposed intermediate. The rate constant increases, and the activation energy decreases with a decrease in the electronegativity of the metal ion. It has been observed that the rate constant of dehalogenation of chloroform using a square planar complex is higher than that using a tetrahedral complex. The data of activation entropy and enthalpy changes follow the isokinetic relationship which confirms the importance of structural factors of Schiff base complexes in the dehalogenation of chloroform.

THE amine exchange reaction between Ni (*N-R*, salim)₂ and diamine in chloroform involves a dehalogenation reaction of chloroform¹ and depends on the basicity of the substituent R². It is an important observation that the dehalogenation reaction of chloroform does not take place in the absence of the metal ion to a measurable extent. These results prompted us to study the effect of softness of the central metal ion on this dehalogenation reaction by keeping identical R and diamine. The present work reports such a study using *bis*(*N-n*-butyl, salim) M(II) [with M(II)=Zn(II), Cu(II), Ni(II), Pt(II) and Pd(II)].

Experimental

All metal Schiff base complexes, *bis*(*N-n*-butyl, salim) M(II) [with M(II)=Zn(II), Cu(II), Ni(II), Pt(II) and Pd(II)] were prepared by using the procedures reported in the literature³. The purity of the complexes was tested by comparing the data of melting point, elemental analysis and IR spectra with that reported in the literature^{4,5}.

The experimental procedure for the study of the kinetics of the dehalogenation reaction is similar to that reported previously by us² (Table 1). A separate experiment was carried out to determine the nature of product of the dehalogenation reaction of chloroform. The general procedure is given below: To 250 ml of chloroform were added [*bis*(*N-n*-butyl, salim)] metal(II) (0.0024 mole) and *N, N, N', N'*-tetramethyl ethylene diamine (0.0167 mole). The solution was allowed to reflux for twenty four hours, during which time a colour change was noted. The colours of the precipitates obtained for a reaction with copper(II) and platinum(II) complexes were yellow, with palladium(II) brown and with zinc(II) orange. The products were identified by

IR spectra, elemental analysis and melting point (Table 2).

The elemental analysis of C and H were done at the Microanalytical Division of the University Department. Infrared spectra were determined using nujol and hexachlorobutadiene mulls on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. The ¹H n.m.r. spectra were determined on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer at 90 MHz using CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS for lock signal. The electrical conductivity measurements in solution were done on Toshniwal conductivity bridge type CLO1/02A.

The syntheses of four complexes in which one coordinated Schiff base is replaced by diamine have been reported for the first time.

Discussion

The mechanism for the dehalogenation reaction of chloroform catalysed by Ni (*N-R*, salim)₂ in presence of diamine involves a seven-coordinated activated complex (Fig. 1). Such an expansion of coordination with diamine and chloroform will be favoured by the soft metal ions. Among the metal ions used in the present work platinum(II) and palladium(II) are softer as compared to copper(II) and nickel(II). Comparatively fast dehalogenation reaction is therefore expected using complexes with palladium(II) and platinum(II). The experimental observations are according to this prediction.

For the related metal ions such as copper(II), nickel(II), platinum(II) and palladium(II) in a similar environment the electronegativity of the metal ion may be considered grossly as a measure of the softness of

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TABLE 1—KINETICS OF DEHALOGENATION OF CHLOROFORM

No.	Complex	Temp. $t^\circ \pm 0.2$	Pseudo first order rate constant $k \times 10^4$	Energy of activation E_a , kcal/mole ± 0.2	Entropy of activation ΔS^\ddagger , e.u.	Enthalpy of activation, ΔH^\ddagger , kcal/mole ± 0.2	Chemical shift, δ C-H ppm	Electronegativity*	Geometry of the complex**
1.	<i>Bis</i> (N- <i>n</i> -butyl, salim) zinc(II)	60.0	0.91	18.9	-23.2	18.2	8.15	1.66	Zn-N ₂ O ₂ , tetrahedral
		65.0	1.29						
		70.0	2.30						
		75.0	2.96						
2.	<i>Bis</i> (N- <i>n</i> -butyl, salim) copper(II)	60.0	1.05	17.3	-27.5	16.6	-	1.75	Cu-N ₂ O ₂ , <i>trans</i> planar stepped
		65.0	1.51						
		70.0	2.70						
		75.0	3.20						
3.	<i>Bis</i> (N- <i>n</i> -butyl, salim) nickel(II)	60.0	1.20	16.1	-30.7	15.4	10.5	1.75	Ni-N ₂ O ₂ , <i>trans</i> planar, isomorphous with Cu-N ₂ O ₂
		65.0	1.90						
		67.0	3.00						
		75.0	3.65						
4.	<i>Bis</i> (N- <i>n</i> -butyl, salim) palladium(II)	60.0	1.35	14.2	-36.0	13.5	7.59	1.35	Pd-N ₂ O ₂ , <i>trans</i> planar
		65.0	2.12						
		70.0	3.13						
		75.0	3.80						
5.	<i>Bis</i> (N- <i>n</i> -butyl, salim) platinum(II)	60.0	1.30	15.1	-33.6	14.4	7.87	1.44	Pt-N ₂ O ₂ , <i>trans</i> planar
		65.0	2.00						
		70.0	3.05						
		75.0	3.70						

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TABLE 2 - ANALYTICAL DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES, M(C₁₇H₃₀N₂OCl), OBTAINED AFTER DEHALOGENATION OF CHLOROFORM

M	Required				Found				m.p. ^o d.c.	Group frequency cm ⁻¹			Molar conductivity in water ^o ohm ⁻¹ cm ²
	%C	%H	%N	%Cl	%C	%H	%N	%Cl		C=N	CH ₂ -N	M-Cl	
Zn	51.9	7.6	10.7	9.0	could not be done	-	10.4	8.7	195-198	1572	1363	375	55.8
Cu	52.2	7.7	10.7	9.1	52.6	7.7	10.3	8.8	237-240	1559	1360	390	45.7
Pd	47.0	5.7	8.0	6.8	46.6	5.4	8.2	6.8	220-224	1578	1370	315	52.2
Pt	39.0	6.9	9.7	8.2	38.7	7.0	9.4	8.4	217-220	1575	1366	290	51.0

* of Ni (C₁₇H₃₀N₂OCl), 49.4 ohm⁻¹ cm².

the metal ion. For these metal ions with the same oxidation state, the softness will increase with a decrease in electronegativity. Thus the electronegativity of the metal ion and the activation energy of the dehalogenation reactions should follow the same trend. The observed increasing trends are given below :

Trend of electronegativity : Pd < Pt < Zn < Ni ~ Cu ... (1)
 Trend of activation energy : Pd < Pt < Ni < Cu < Zn ... (2)

Although the electronegativity values of nickel and copper are the same, the activation energy of the dehalogenation reaction using these two complexes differ by as much as 1.2 kcal/mole. On the basis of the polarization effect, nickel(II) is softer than copper(II)⁶. The observed lower value of activation energy for a reaction catalysed by nickel(II) complex fits well with this order of softness. Zinc(II) with the electronic configuration 3d¹⁰ is expected to be harder than copper(II) for the dehalogenation reaction catalysed by zinc(II) complex.

Fig. 1. Seven coordinated intermediate.

 Fig. 2. Isokinetic relationship for the ligand substitution reaction of *bis* (*N-n*-butyl, salim) M (II)

As it has been observed with *bis* (*N-R*, salim)₂ nickel(II)³ the activation entropy change for the dehalogenation reaction of chloroform by using other metal complexes is also negative. This observation supports the proposed activated complex which takes up one more ligand from the medium. The solvation also contributes to the negative change in entropy. As the entropy changes of a reaction using palladium(II) and platinum(II) complexes are of the same order and are lower than that using nickel(II) complex, the coordination sphere of the activated complex containing these metal ions is expected to be similar. It may be noted here that a seven membered activated complex has been suggested for nickel(II) complex. The comparatively small negative entropy change for the reaction using *bis* (*n*-butyl, salim)₂ zinc(II) as compared to that using other complexes, however, suggests that the ligation entropy contribution of bidentate ligands to the total entropy change depends on metal ion. The

same ligand containing two coordination centres may act as a bidentate for some metal ions, and may act as a monodentate for other metal ions. One may say with caution that one of the ligands *N-n*-butyl, salim and diamine containing two coordinating centres behaves as a monodentate ligand for Zn(II) and these ligands behave as the bidentate ligands for other metal ions in the activated complex.

The activation enthalpy of the dehalogenation reaction directly reflects the extent of the change in the metal-ligand orbital overlap in *bis*-(*N-n*-butyl, salim) metal(II). A change in the ground state geometry during reaction will have an additional contribution to the total enthalpy. The dehalogenation reaction using *bis* (*N-n*-butyl salim)₂ zinc(II) involves the geometrical change of the complex. The total activation enthalpy will be therefore large for (*N-n*-butyl, salim)₂ zinc (II). The experimental observation substantiates this analysis. On the basis of the softness of metal ions among the planar complexes, the activation energy of a reaction using *bis* (*N-n*-butyl, salim) palladium(II), will be the least. The observed increasing trend of the activation enthalpy (except for using Zn²⁺ complex) of the dehalogenation reaction is decreasing trend of the softness of the metal ion. An excellent relation⁷ between the activation entropy change and the activation enthalpy change for the series of complexes studied in the present work has been observed (Fig. 2).

A comparison of the chemical shift of the azomethine proton (δ_{C-H}) with the electronegativity of the central metal ion gives an interesting observation. ¹H n.m.r. spectra of copper(II) complex could not be analysed due to the paramagnetic broadening. Nickel(II) complex is planar and is diamagnetic. It has sharp ¹H n.m.r. spectra. A decreasing trend of δ_{C-H} and of electronegativity of metal ion are identical. The percent covalent character of M-N bond depends on the electronegativity of metal ion in related metal complexes. Thus the trend in δ_{C-H} can be correlated with M-N bond covalency⁶. If the polarization effects controlling the shielding constant of γ -CH were also equally important in the dehalogenation reaction of chloroform catalysed by the imine complex, the decreasing trend of δ_{C-H} of the activation energy of the dehalogenation reaction would be identical. It is interesting that all complexes except zinc(II) complex show a good correlation. This observation suggests that in addition to the polarization effects, the geometrical factors have influence on the kinetics of the reaction under consideration.

The mechanism for the reactions studied in the present work involves both the ligand-substitution reaction and the dehalogenation of chloroform¹. One of the supporting evidences for this mechanism is the separation of the proposed complex chloro (*N, N, N', N'*-tetramethylene-diamine-*N-n*-butyl salicylaldiminato) metal(II). Such complexes with copper(II), palladium(II), platinum(II) and zinc(II) are separated for the first time (Table 2) from the dehalogenation reaction

of chloroform using the respective complexes as a catalyst. These complexes may be five coordinate species, ionic complexes or intimate ion-pairs. The data of electrical conductivity and ir spectra are little confusing. These complexes give nonconducting solutions in nitrobenzene, and the molar conductivities of aqueous solutions ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) are in the range 40 to 55 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ (Table 2). A medium intensity band due to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ has been observed in the range 390 cm^{-1} to 290 cm^{-1} depending on M. The x-ray crystallographic data will be therefore be required to decide the configuration of these complexes.

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